

Stubborn Architecture—Annotated Bibliography

When I share recent studies on knowledge production with colleagues—especially those who were hired before the Great Recession—they often respond with some variant of “I’d never seen these numbers before” or “I didn’t realize things were this bad.” If you want to get an accurate sense of the current state of academic anthropology and work to change things for the better, the research below offers a primer. I also recommend the presentations given as part of the Wenner-Gren Foundation workshop “The Sociopolitics of Knowledge Production in Archaeology and Anthropology,” which I co-organized with Laura Heath-Stout in 2023. Videos and transcripts of all presentations will be available at www.anthroknowledge.com until October 2028, when our funding for the website runs out.

Black Trowel Collective. Black Trowel Collective manifesto.

<https://blacktrowelcollective.wordpress.com/2020/06/17/btc-manifesto/>

The Black Trowel Collective (BTC) manifesto outlines mutual-aid principles and scaffolds a support network for archaeologists based on core anarchist principles. Think “self-organization, voluntary association, [and] mutual aid” (Graeber 2004:3) rather than the pop culture image of black balaclavas and Molotov cocktails. BTC also distributes microgrants to archaeology students in need, an initiative entirely funded by donations and member labor. If you have the financial capacity, I recommend donating to their Patreon (<https://www.patreon.com/blacktrowelmicrogrants>).

Bradford, D. J., & Crema, E. R. (2022). Risk factors for the occurrence of sexual misconduct during archaeological and anthropological fieldwork. *American Anthropologist*, 124(3), 548-559. <https://doi.org/10.1111/aman.13763>

Are you advising students about participation in field projects? Do you want to run a safe field project? This study examines the risk factors for sexual misconduct during fieldwork. The authors of this study surveyed 300 archaeologists and anthropologists from a range of countries about their experiences. They found that longer field seasons and projects without clearly communicated and enforced policies are more likely to facilitate misconduct. Their results also showed clear patterns related to identity and directionality, with low risks of consequences for perpetrators and high risks of abuse or harassment directed at marginalized individuals.

Clancy, K. B., Nelson, R. G., Rutherford, J. N., & Hinde, K. (2014). Survey of academic field experiences (SAFE): Trainees report harassment and assault. *PloS one*, 9(7), e102172. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0102172>

I distinctly remember the reverberations of this publication, which came out when I was in grad school. Written by a team of anthropologists, the Survey of Academic Field Experiences (SAFE) study surveyed 668 field scientists across a wide range of disciplines (archaeologists, biologists, zoologists, geologists, etc.) to investigate harassment and assault in fieldwork contexts. Their results were alarming: 21.7% of respondents had personally experienced sexual assault and 64% had personally experienced sexual harassment. Harassment and assault were overwhelmingly aimed at trainees, and women were significantly more likely to

have experienced harassment and assault than men. When men were harassed or assaulted, the perpetrators were more likely to be peers; when women were harassed or assaulted, the perpetrators were more likely to be superiors. Most respondents had not encountered explicit codes of conduct or sexual harassment policies at their field sites, and only 20.6% were aware of mechanisms for reporting harassment. See Figure 3 for a visual representation of respondent experiences of harassment and assault, as well as experiences of reporting mechanisms and outcomes across the sample. In total, these results reveal that “conducting research in the field exposes scientists to a number of negative experiences as targets and bystanders,” (4) shedding light on “a systemic and substantial degree of problematic behavior within scientific disciplines” (5). The authors conclude by emphasizing the role of supervisors and principal investigators in creating workplace cultures where harassment and assault are not tolerated. Nelson et al. (2017)—a paper by the same team of co-authors—should be read as a companion piece, as it extends the findings of the SAFE study and provides suggestions for enforcing the codes of conduct and systems of accountability that correlate with equitable, safe, and positive fieldwork experiences (see Figure 2 and pp.716–719).

Colaninno, C. E., Lambert, S. P., Beahm, E. L., & Drexler, C. G. (2020). Creating and supporting a harassment- and assault-free field school. *Advances in Archaeological Practice*, 8(2), 111–122. <https://doi:10.1017/aap.2020.8>

Colaninno et al. build on National Academy of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine (NASEM) recommendations for preventing harassment and assault in academy to develop a set of best practices for archaeological field schools. Most field schools exhibit some of the five risk factors that NASEM correlates with sexual harassment, including a perceived tolerance for sexually inappropriate behaviour, males dominating the work setting and leadership, hierarchical power structures, a focus on policy compliance, and a disregard for measures intended to reduce or eliminate inappropriate behavior. See Table 2 for a clear summary of actionable changes that field directors can implement.

Earle, B., DelPo Kulow, M. (2015) The “deeply toxic” damage caused by the abolition of mandatory retirement and its collision with tenure in higher education: A proposal for statutory repair. *Southern California Interdisciplinary Law Journal*, 24(2): 369–418.

Earle and DelPo Kulow examine the unintended consequences of the intersection of tenure as an institution with the abolition of mandatory retirement ages in the US. The authors evaluate the impact of the 1986 amendments to the Age Discrimination in Employment Act (ADEA) from a legal perspective. Although these amendments were intended to ensure that retirement decisions were performance-based, rather than age-based, they had immediate reverberations across American higher education (see Speakman et al. 2018b: Figure 5) once an exception was lifted in the mid-1990s. The authors underscore that the few other professions in the U.S. allow people to have permanent employment contracts without mandatory retirement have built-in checks and balances—there are caps on the benefit systems of public-school teachers that disincentivize working beyond age 70, for example, while federal judges are subject to public scrutiny and the possibility of impeachment. In contrast, “understanding why more professors continue to work past seventy is simple math” (415). Each additional year of employment adds to faculty income in an economic climate that has seen diminished retirement portfolios and rising healthcare costs, particularly after the 2008 recession. This

clear incentive structure is borne out by the numbers— between 2000 and 2011, for example, the number of professors in US education over sixty-five years of age more than doubled. The protection afforded by tenure means that permanent faculty cannot be let go unless there is difficult-to-prove “just cause,” leading to demographic and intellectual stagnation in the academy. Earle and Delo Kulow also emphasize, however, that senior faculty can certainly continue to make important contributions to research, teaching, and service, and that the free speech protections afforded by tenure are essential to fostering intellectual interchange in the academy. They propose a solution that foregrounds “the larger good of the university” (394), in which there is a mandatory cap on tenure, which expires at age 70, whereafter it is replaced with an employment contract renewable on an annual or multi-year basis. See Section V, pp. 410–414, for their suggested framework for a Congressional re-adoption of pre-1986 statutory language regarding tenure, mandatory retirement, and higher education.

Dennis, D., Docot, D., Gendron, D., & Gershon, I. (2022). The worst of anthro job ads for 2021. *American Anthropologist*, 124(4), 900-905.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/aman.13781>

Creative activism on display. Dennis et al. developed a contest for the worst job ad in anthropology, which included sending plaques to the winning departments. The exercise was intended to “remind departments that job ads can be written with more consideration and care for applicants and that their carelessness has costs that applicants and letter writers are paying (and resenting every moment of)” (900). Their recommendations include requiring only a cover letter and CV during the first round and asking for additional documents during the second round, transparency about salary, benefits and teaching/service loads, and being deliberate and critical about recommendation letters. A useful read if your department is hiring.

Flewellen, A. O., Dunnivant, J. P., Odewale, A., Jones, A., Wolde-Michael, T., Crossland, Z., & Franklin, M. (2021). “The future of archaeology is antiracist”: Archaeology in the time of Black Lives Matter. *American Antiquity*, 86(2), 224–243.
<https://doi:10.1017/aaq.2021.18>

This co-authored AAQ forum piece is drawn from the salon “Archaeology in the Time of Black Lives Matter” that was held in June 2020, co-sponsored by the Society of Black Archaeologists, the North American Theoretical Archaeology Group, and the Columbia Center for Archaeology. The article presents a Black feminist approach to developing and practicing an anti-racist archaeology; traditional hierarchical assumptions about and attitudes towards knowledge production are flagged throughout, with alternatives provided. The panelists and authors chart the contours of Black feminist archaeology as a praxis rooted in Black study and Black feminism, grounded in community-led projects. See p.232 for a list of institutional changes that foster equity on campus, rather than just diversity, and p.233 for the four phases of building an antiracist archaeology.

Heath-Stout, L. E., (2022). The invisibly disabled archaeologist. *International Journal of Historical Archaeology*, 27:17–32. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10761-022-00653-8>

This study draws from Heath-Stout’s larger project exploring sexism, racism, and heterosexism in archaeology to focus in on a sample of respondents with self-disclosed

disabilities. Drawing theory from disability studies, she analyses interview data to demonstrate how assumptions of compulsory able-bodiedness permeate the discipline. Respondents with invisible disabilities highlighted the intricate individual calculations required to either “pass” or disclose their disability. While such disclosures can allow for accommodation, they also open up the potential for discrimination. The significant time and energy devoted to making such decisions would be better dedicated to archaeological research, which is another stressor, as the punitive demands of contemporary academia rarely allow for the “crip time” necessary to care for oneself. Heath-Stout emphasizes that “we must not only examine disabled lives in the past but also transform the material realities of our discipline in the present” (28). To facilitate such a transformation, she lists a range of actionable recommendations on pp. 29–30. Most suggestions highlight the capacity of individuals in supervisory or teaching roles to improve experiences of colleagues or students with disabilities. Strategies include being aware that most groups of archaeologists will include some individuals with disabilities, being proactive about accommodations if you are in a supervisory position, and open-mindedness and flexibility involving timelines and approaches to learning

Ike, N., Miller, G., & Hartemann, G. O. (2020). Anti-racist archaeology. Your time is now. *The SAA Archaeological Record*, 20(4), 12–16.

Published in September 2020 this piece provides a trenchant discussion of the emotional and intellectual labor demanded of Black archaeologists. Explicitly foregrounding their own positionalities and diverse perspectives, Ike et al. frame the piece to explicitly task white archaeologists with interrogating their responsibility for making archaeology anti-racist, with a focus on “real, tangible, actionable changes” (13). Ike underscores the need to center Black people as knowledge producers while encouraging white archaeologists to actually do the work and engage with the many antiracist resources that already exist. Miller offers a biting “emotional labour invoice” (Figure 1) that is reminiscent of the incisively funny activism that undergirds the “Worst Anthropology Job Ad”: competition (Dennis et al. 2022, see above), or “Bingo for Anthropologists of Color” (Docot 2017). Like Ike, Miller underscores the exhaustion felt by Black archaeologists of all career stages. In the face of pervasive institutional attitudes to antiracist education and diversity and inclusion efforts as “extracurricular rather than essential”(14), Miller concludes by demanding that Black scholars be compensated for their labor. Finally, Hartemann broadens these issues beyond North America, emphasizing how colonialism and racism are woven into foundational assumptions about language, scholarship, and knowledge production. Disentangling these threads requires white archaeologists from the Global North to evaluate who they are (and are not) reading, citing, and teaching, and to understand that antiracist practices requires “giv[ing] up certain traditional notions of power and expertise that are embedded in the field” (15). On p.16, they conclude with a list of Black archaeologists to read, cite, and include in course syllabi, along with organizations to consider supporting.

Kawa, N. C., Clavijo Michelangeli, J. A., Clark, J. L., Ginsberg, D., & McCarty, C. (2019). The social network of US academic anthropology and its inequalities. *American Anthropologist*, 121(1), 14–29. <https://doi.org/10.1111/aman.13158>

Who actually gets hired in American academic anthropology? Using social network analysis, these authors examine hiring demographics in the academy relative to PhD granting institution. Their study explores the impact of proxies for productivity (average publications

per faculty), prestige (average citations per faculty, awards per faculty member, and GRE score of admitted graduate students), and institutional resources (indexed by endowment) on patterns of hiring. Kawa et al. draw data on faculty composition from the AAA database and departmental websites to explore network reciprocity, network centrality and core-periphery structure in American academic anthropology. They find that “In US academic anthropology, a small cluster of programs is responsible for producing the majority of tenured and tenure-track faculty in PhD-granting programs, with a very select few dominating the network” (23). A sobering read, unless you’re affiliated with the University of Chicago. See Table 2 and Figures 2 and 3 for a useful summary.

Mackie, M., & Rockwell, H. (2023). Beyond market share: Accounting for doctoral program size in recent rates of anthropology faculty job placement. *PLoS One*. 18(5): e0285330. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0285330>

This study builds upon and expands earlier research out of the University of Georgia which examined faculty hiring dynamics in anthropology and archaeology using market share as a measure of program dominance. Market share represents what proportion of the overall market is held by graduates from a particular program (e.g. in the 2019–2020 academic year, 4.9% of the market in tenure-track jobs in anthropology departments was held by University of Chicago PhDs). Because this measure focuses only on successful job placements rather than the total pool of job seekers, the market share metric cannot control for the effects of program size. Mackie and Rockwell turn to placement rates to address this shortcoming, evaluating the number of program graduates placed in tenure-track positions relative to the total number of program graduates (e.g. in the 2019–2020 academic year, NYU had placed 28.8% of its graduates from the preceding two decades into tenure-track positions). Using data from the AAAs *AnthroGuide* to compile a list of PhD-granting institutions and data from the National Center for Education Statistics, the authors found that many small- to medium-sized programs were as successful as large programs at placing their graduates into tenure-track positions in anthropology. However, their results also highlighted that “... of the more than 10,500 graduates between 2000 to 2019, only 1829, or 17.1% held TT jobs in the fall [of] of 2019” (6). On p. 10–11, the authors make a series of recommendations for the programs, faculty, and graduate students who are faced with this reality, underscoring that “in today’s market the majority of graduate students will find employment outside of tenure track positions” (11).

Souleles, D. (2020, September). What to do with the predator in your bibliography. *Allegra lab: Anthropology for radical optimism*. Accessed 26 September 2025. <https://allegralaboratory.net/what-to-do-with-the-predator-in-your-bibliography/>

In this Allegra piece, Souleles tackles the thorny problem of citational politics when living scholars, who still benefit from academic references to their work, have been recognized as bad actors who perpetrate harm. In his framing—“how should we think about a person’s scholarship when they’ve done things we think are bad?” and “what obligation does someone have to citing an academic’s work when they personally object to the bad things that a person has done...?” Souleles focuses on a citational dilemma specific to a now-published manuscript about Khipu accounting practices (see Bikales 2020a,b for context). Rather than abandoning the paper—a costly option for early career scholars—he outlines an approach that entails “1) acknowledgement, 2) comparative scrutiny and provision of alternatives, and 3) eventual transcendence” rather than complete erasure. He discovered, however, that the

journal would not publish his accepted article with the explanatory note due to concerns about libel (see the Overholtzer and Jalbert 2021 corrigendum for more examples of this dynamic). At the last minute, Souleles resorted to substituting a generic dedication to those working to make archaeology safe. Though an unsatisfying solution, the *Allegra* piece itself does the work of marking a predatory scholar and drawing an attention to this recurring academic dilemma.

Voss, B. L. (2021a). Disrupting cultures of harassment in archaeology: Social-environmental and trauma-informed approaches to disciplinary transformation. *American Antiquity*, 86(3), 447– 464. <https://doi:10.1017/aaq.2021.19>

This piece should be read in concert with Voss 2021b, which outlines the extent of harassment and assault in archaeology. This second piece identifies five key obstacles to changing disciplinary culture and offers multiscale interventions to confront these obstacles, building on Voss' 35 years of experience in the sector across the spheres of cultural resource management, museums, and academia. Normalization, in which cultures of harassment are learned and produced intergenerationally, and exclusionary processes that reward risk-taking and punish complainants, are the first two key barriers to change. Fraternalization, or intimate relationships among colleagues, gatekeeping and restriction of access to data, resources, and social networks, and structural and cultural obstacles to reporting constitute the remaining three barriers. To disrupt these archaeology's 'cultures of harassment', Voss turns to two evidence-based frameworks from public health. The first is a social-environmental model which understands public health problems as emerging from reciprocal interactions between individuals, social relationships, communities and organizations. The second are trauma-informed approaches to interventions to combat discrimination, harassment, and sexual violence; these are founded upon the acknowledgement that most archaeologists are likely to have experienced or witnessed harassment or assault, retraumatization of survivors is likely without significant cultural change, and both individual and collective action can promote positive environments. Voss uses the 2019 Society for American Archaeology meetings as a case study in which these principles were deployed effectively. The remainder of the paper (pp. 455–460) is dedicated to detailing interventions at multiple scales—societal, community and organizational, relational, and individual—that provide “best practices for preventing harassment, supporting survivors, and holding harassers accountable for their actions” (455).

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